

IMPORTANT TECHNIQUES TO SOLVE FUNCTIONAL EQUATIONS

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ABSTRACT

Functional equations appear frequently in Mathematical Olympiads. In this article we focus on some types of functional equations and how to solve them.

Key words: Functional, equation, inequality, real number, positive, symmetric.

АННОТАЦИЯ

Функциональные уравнения часто появляются на математических олимпиадах. В этой статье мы сосредоточимся на некоторых типах функциональных уравнений и способах их решения

Ключевые слова: функциональный, уравнение, неравенство, настоящий номер, положительный, симметричный.

I.Switching

The main idea is to exchange the variables if one side of equation is symmetric with regard to the variables.

Problem 1.

Find all functions $f : R \rightarrow R$ such that,

$$f(f(x) + f(y)) = f(x^2) + 2x^2 f(y) + f^2(y) \text{ holds for all } x, y \in R \quad (1)$$

Solution: Let $p(x, y)$ denote the assertion (1). Left hand side is symmetric, by switching x, y we can see that

$$p(x, y) : f(f(y) + f(x)) = f(y^2) + 2y^2 f(x) + f^2(x) \quad (2)$$

From (1) and (2) we get that:

$$f(x^2) + 2x^2 f(y) + f^2(y) = f(y^2) + 2y^2 f(x) + f^2(x)$$

By taking $y = 0$ and $y = 1$ we obtain that:

$$\begin{cases} f(x^2) + 2x^2 f(0) + f^2(0) = f(0) + f^2(x) \\ f(x^2) + 2x^2 f(1) + f^2(1) = f(1) + 2f(x) + f^2(x) \end{cases} \quad (3)$$

From (3), we can easily get the answers $f(x) = 0, \forall x \in R$ or

$$f(x) = x^2, \forall x \in R$$

Problem 2.

Find all functions $f : R \rightarrow R$ such that,

$$f(x) + y + f(f(x) + y) = 2f(x + y) \quad (4)$$

Solution: $f(f(x) + y) = 2f(x + y) - f(x) - y$

$$p(x, f(y)) : f(f(x) + f(y)) = 2f(x + f(y)) - f(x) - f(y) = \Rightarrow \\ = 2(2f(x + y) - x - f(y)) - f(x) - f(y)$$

$$\Rightarrow f(f(x) + f(y)) = 4f(x + y) - 3f(y) - f(x) - 2x \quad (5)$$

By switching variables:

$$f(f(y) + f(x)) = 4f(y + x) - 3f(x) - f(y) - 2y \quad (6)$$

From (5) and (6) we can obtain :

$$f(x) - x = f(y) - y$$

By taking $y = 0 \Rightarrow f(x) = x + C$ by putting this solution to (4) we find

$$C = 0, \text{ then } f(x) = x.$$

II. Flipped inequalities.

A general idea is to use two inequalities for finding the value of f at a certain point. To this we will show $f(a) \geq c$ and $f(a) \leq c$, to obtain $f(a) = c$

In the following problem we will find $f(1)$ by this method.

Problem 3. Find all functions $f : \mathbb{R}^+ \rightarrow \mathbb{R}^+$ such that for all positive real numbers x, y such that $x > y$ we have:

$$f(x-y) = f(x) - f(y) \cdot f\left(\frac{1}{x}\right)y$$

Solution: We start the proof with the following claim.

Claim1: $\forall x \in \mathbb{R}^+$ we have $f(x) \leq x$.

Proof: Since $f(x-y) > 0$, we get that $f(x) - f(x)f\left(\frac{1}{x}\right)y > 0$

$$f(x)\left(1 - yf\left(\frac{1}{x}\right)\right) > 0 \rightarrow f\left(\frac{1}{x}\right) < \frac{1}{y} \text{ for } x > y.$$

By choosing y close enough to x we obtain that

$$f\left(\frac{1}{x}\right) \leq \frac{1}{x} \Rightarrow f(x) \leq x.$$

Claim 2. $f(1) = 1$

Proof. We know $f(1) \leq 1$, so we must prove $f(1) \geq 1$.

Let $y < 1$. By plugging $x = 1$ we take

$$1 - y \geq f(1 - y) = f(1) - f^2(1)y$$

$$1 - y \geq f(1) - f^2(1)y$$

$$(f(1) - 1)(y(1 + f(1)) - 1) \geq 0$$

We take $\forall y$ which $1 > y > \frac{1}{1 + f(1)}$ and we get $f(1) \geq 1 \Rightarrow f(1) = 1$

Claim 3. $\forall z < 1$ $f(z) = z$ we take $x = 1, y = 1 - z, z < 1$

$$f(z) = 1 - (1 - z) = z$$

Now we take $y < x < 1$,

$$x - y = f(x - y) = f(x) - f(x)f\left(\frac{1}{x}\right)y = x - xyf\left(\frac{1}{x}\right)$$

$$\Rightarrow f\left(\frac{1}{x}\right) = \frac{1}{x} \text{ for } x > 1. \text{ Therefore } f(x) = x \text{ for } \forall x \in R$$

Overall that kind of problems are common in mathematical olympiads. We recommend to solve some functional equations by using this techniques.

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